

1 **Junctional activity at the cell membrane during transformation of the cervix resulting from**
2 **high-risk HPV infection.**

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We studied transformation in vivo in humans in the cervix by using next-generation technologies to
8 measure total transcription before and during the course of cancer development. Gap junction protein beta
9 (GJB7), tight junction protein 2 (TJP2), claudin 4 and cadherin 3 were all enriched during the course of
10 cancer progression in vivo. We observed a broader role for TJP2 in the progression to transformation in
11 humans. Junctional activity is informative for understanding of transformation status.
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